

Supporting Information

To investigate the effect of the nano- and microscale topographical cues on the contraction of heart cells, HL-1 cells were seeded onto the wavy scaffold, and fluorescent immunostaining of the scaffolds was performed after 7 days of culture. As presented on Figure S1, HL-1 cells expressed myocardial sacromeric α -actinin and connexin-43, while the nuclei were visualized by Hoechst staining. The presence of the cardiac proteins could indicate some degree of sarcomere organization and electrophysiological coupling of the HL-1 cells.

Figure S1 Immunofluorescent staining of HL-1 cells expressing α -actinin (red) and connexin 43 (green) with Hoechst staining of the nuclei (blue) (scale bar = 200 μ m)